

Formation Constants of the Chelates of 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene-*ortho*-Fluoroaniline with Some Bivalent Metal Ions

M. S. MAYADBO*, A. M. CHAUBAL and S. H. HUSSAIN

Department of Chemistry, Ramnarain Ruia College, Matunga, Bombay-400 019

Manuscript received 26 March 1979, revised 18 February 1982, accepted 23 May 1982

Potentiometric studies on metal chelates of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and UO_2^{2+} with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-*ortho*-fluoroaniline have been carried out. The formation constant, pK_{11} , of the reagent and the formation constants of its metal chelates have been determined by Bjerrum's method at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and at ionic strength 0.1 *M* in 75 : 25 percent (v/v) dioxane-water medium. The order of stability of metal chelates is found to be $\text{UO}_2^{2+} > \text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{Zn}^{2+} > \text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+}$.

A survey of literature indicates that no systematic study of the stabilities of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-*o*-fluoroaniline and its metal chelates with bivalent metal ions has been carried out. The present communication, therefore, deals with the determination of the stability constants of the chelates of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-*o*-fluoroaniline in 75% (v/v) dioxane-water medium employing the Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹.

Experimental

A precision research pH meter, Corning Model 12, with a wide range glass electrode and calomel reference electrode was used for pH measurements. The meter has an arrangement for normal and expanded scales. The smallest division on the expanded scale is 0.005 pH unit.

The ligand, 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-*o*-fluoroaniline, was prepared and repeatedly crystallised from alcohol to get an analytically pure sample (m.p. 104°). The purity of the ligand was ascertained by elemental analysis. The carbon and hydrogen content of the fluoro compound was determined by the method described by Steyermark². Fluorine was determined by the volumetric procedure of Schoniger³. (Found: C, 76.8; H, 4.30; N, 5.20; F, 6.90. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{FNO}$; C, 76.98; H, 4.53; N, 5.28; F, 7.17%).

All the chemicals used except the ligand and the perchloric acid were of B. D. H. analytical grade. The perchloric acid was E. Merck G. R. grade. The medium of titration was a 75% (v/v) dioxane-water mixture. The dioxane used was purified by the method described by Vogel⁴. Distilled water, redistilled over alkaline potassium permanganate, was used throughout the investigation. Sodium perchlorate was added to maintain a constant ionic strength (0.1 *M*). The titrations were carried out in an inert atmosphere by bubbling oxygen free

nitrogen gas through the solutions. Metal perchlorates were prepared from the oxides or carbonates and standardised complexometrically by EDTA⁵. Measurements were carried out at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

The following solutions were titrated potentiometrically against standard carbonate free sodium hydroxide solution (1.01 *M*):

- (i) 5 ml 0.16 *M* HClO_4 + 5 ml 0.64 *M* NaClO_4 + 30 ml dioxane.
- (ii) 5 ml 0.16 *M* HClO_4 + 5 ml 0.64 *M* NaClO_4 + requisite amount of the reagent to give 0.004 *M* reagent concentration in the final solution + 30 ml dioxane.
- (iii) 5 ml 0.64 *M* NaClO_4 + 5 ml 0.008 *M* metal salt solution in 0.16 *M* HClO_4 + requisite amount of the reagent to give 0.004 *M* reagent concentration in the final solution + 30 ml dioxane.

All titrations were performed in duplicate to test for reproducibility. The results are depicted in Fig. 1.

The experimental method of Irving and Rossotti¹ was applied to find out the values of $\bar{n}$ and pL .

Results and Discussion

In the ligand, it is the phenolic OH group that takes part in complex formation and the proton is replaced by metal ions during chelation. Since only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated during complexation, Y , the number of dissociable protons attached per ligand molecule is one.

From the titration curves using solutions (i) and (ii), $\bar{n}_A$ values at various B values (pH meter readings) were calculated, and the curve of B against the corresponding $\bar{n}_A$ values was plotted. The formation curve extends over a range $0.18 < \bar{n}_A < 0.97$. This indicates the formation of the species

Fig. 1. Titration curves of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-o-fluoroaniline.

HL only. The value of pK_1^H could be determined from the half-integral point at $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$.

The maximum values of $\bar{n}$ for Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Zn^{2+} systems range from 0.606 to 0.998 indicating the formation of 1:1 complexes only. Precipitation in these systems occurs at $B = 6.4, 7.2, 6.9$ and 6.6 , respectively. Since the maximum value of $\bar{n}$ obtained at the point of incipient precipitation is 1.0, $\log K_2$ for the above systems could not be determined by the reported method. For UO_2^{2+} , precipitation does not occur till $B = 5.32$ at which point $\bar{n}$ values lie well above 1.5. Both $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ could, therefore, be obtained. Since the difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ for UO_2^{2+} obtained by the half $\bar{n}$ method was less than 1.78 log units, the least square method was used to obtain refined values.

Fig. 2 shows the experimental data ($\bar{n}, pL$) for the metal ligand systems in 75% dioxane-water medium together with theoretical formation curves⁶ calculated from the relationship $\bar{n} + (\bar{n} - 1) K_1(L) + (\bar{n} - 2) K_1 K_2 (L)^2 = 0$.

Values of stability constants for all the systems, except UO_2^{2+} , obtained from the half-integral method were used for the above calculation. For UO_2^{2+} , the values of stability constants obtained from the least square treatment were employed. The curve for Cu^{2+} is in appreciably better agreement with the experimental points. A lower precision is indicated for the systems involving Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} . A more satisfactory agreement

Fig. 2. Formation curves of metal ligand systems of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-o-fluoroaniline.

for these systems could not be obtained since the values of $\log K$, calculated by the method of successive approximations remained within the limits of error.

The most representative values are recorded in Table 1. Standard deviations⁶ and limits of error

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE COMPLEXES OF 2-HYDROXY-1-NAPHTHALIDENE-O-FLUOROANILINE WITH SOME DIVALENT METAL IONS

Cations	$\mu = 0.1 M (NaClO_4)$					
	$t = 25 \pm 0.1^\circ$	UO_2^{2+}	Ni^{2+}	Co^{2+}	Zn^{2+}	
$\log K_1$	9.34	8.47	8.96	5.08	5.25	5.40
$\log K_2$	—	—	7.18	—	—	—

For H^+ , K_1 corresponds to the species LH , while for metal ions K_1 and K_2 correspond to the species ML_1 and ML_2 , respectively.

for $\log K$ values range from ± 0.2 to ± 0.03 and ± 0.13 to ± 0.02 , respectively. The order of stability for the metal chelates was found to be $UO_2^{2+} > Cu^{2+} > Zn^{2+} > Co^{2+} > Ni^{2+}$.

Acknowledgement

The authors sincerely thank Dr. D. G. Vartak, B. A. R. C., Bombay for valuable suggestions and Prof. A. P. Rao, Head, Chemistry Dept., Ramnarain Ruia College for encouragement.

MAYADBO, CHAUBAL & HUSSAIN : FORMATION CONSTANTS OF THE CHELATES ETC.

References

1. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
2. A. STEYERMARK, "Quantitative Organic Microanalysis", Academic Press, Inc., N. Y., 1961, p. 222.
3. W. SCHÖNIGER, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1956, 869.
4. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", 3rd Edn., Longman, p. 177.
5. G. SCHWARZENBACH, "Complexometric Titrations", Methuen and Co. Ltd., London, 1956, p. 60.
6. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397.